

BIOMASS ASH: A STUDY OF ITS LEACHABILITY

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Abstract

In recent years, the energy sector has been preparing for a transition from coal combustion to purely ecological green energy sources. This brings changes that have and will have a significant impact on the construction industry. One of these green energy sources is biomass (BMA). Biomass ashes generally have a high content of chlorides, sulphates and alkalis, which complicates their use in the construction industry. From a legislative perspective, BMA ash is classified as waste.

This study focuses on the leachability of 51 BMA ash samples from six locations in the Czech Republic, produced from grate and fluidized bed combustion of biomass and co-combustion of biomass with coal. The main emphasis was placed on the leachability of heavy metals and other potentially dangerous chemical substances. Simultaneously, pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), soluble inorganic salts (SIS), and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) were measured. It was found that most of the BMA ashes exceed the limits for TDS, chlorides, fluorides, sulphates, chromium, molybdenum, and selenium. Additionally, most of the samples showed excessively high pH and electrical conductivity.

Introduction

Biomass combustion is the most traditional way of obtaining energy, and wood was the most traditional fuel until the Industrial Revolution. With the increasing energy demands of society, it was necessary to switch to an alternative fuel, which was coal. Although society's energy demands continue to rise, there is a greater emphasis on sustainable energy production. Currently, we cannot replace all energy sources that derive energy from coal combustion with "green energy." Therefore, there is currently a large-scale transition to biomass combustion or co-combustion. The CO₂ emissions generated by burning biomass are roughly equivalent to the CO₂ absorbed by the plants burned during their lifetime¹. Because of this, biomass combustion can be considered a carbon-neutral energy source.^{2,3,4}

Biomass is a natural material. Its origin can be either animal or, more commonly, plant. It is one of the most diverse sources of renewable energy and can be used to generate electricity and heat. The properties of biomass are crucial for its subsequent use. Like traditional fuel types, biomass also has basic indicators of its quality. These include humidity content, chemical composition of the fuel, ash content, volatile matter content, and calorific value⁵. The composition of biomass and its ash depends not only on the type of vegetation it comes from but also on subsequent storage and processing.^{1,6}

There are many types of biomass combustion, and several types of ash are produced as a final product, which can be divided into two main groups – fly ash and bottom ash. The most common method is grate combustion⁷. Another method is fluidized bed combustion. This is a more modern method than grate combustion. Due to combustion at lower temperatures, it also reduces the emissions of NO_x and SO_x emitted during combustion^{4,6,7}. Another option is biomass co-combustion with fossil fuels such as coal. This practice is becoming increasingly common in the energy sector and provides an efficient and transitional solution^{1,8,9}.

Ash can be added to concrete mixes for various purposes. Currently, the use of ash is permitted by European legislation only if it is fly ash from coal combustion or co-combustion¹⁰. The main problem encountered when using BMA ash in civil engineering is the instability of its composition. The main problems include high alkali and chloride content, which can have long-term effects on concrete corrosion^{2,10}. Nevertheless, there is potential for utilizing ash produced from biomass combustion or co-combustion in the construction industry, which would make this product a valuable resource instead of waste, which is how biomass ash is currently classified under legislation. This is precisely the focus of this work, which aims to compare the leachability of biomass ash from the perspective of waste intended for landfilling and from the perspective of its potential use in the construction industry, by Technical Conditions 93: Design and Construction of Road Structures Using Fly Ash and Bottom Ash¹¹.

Materials and methods

Ash samples collected between 2021 and 2024 at six locations in the Czech Republic were selected as input materials for the analyses. These locations represent different types of combustion technologies – grate combustion of biomass, grate co-combustion of biomass with coal, and fluidised bed co-combustion (FBC) of coal with biomass. The combusted materials were bark, mixtures of hay and straw, wood chips, sawdust and coal. The output of these processes was bottom ash (**BA**), fly ash (**FA**) or a combination of both (**FA+BA**). Three representative samples were selected from each location according to the type of resulting ash. A total of 23 samples were analysed, and their specifications are described in Table I.

Table I: Overview of analysed samples

label	method of combustion	combusted material	type of ash	location
LBP_FA LBP_BA	grate combustion	bark	FA BA	Lenzing Biocel Paskov a.s (LBP)
JH_FA+BA	grate combustion	hay and straw in	FA+BA	Energetické centrum s.r.o. Jindřichův Hradec (JH)
CZTL_BA	grate co-combustion	woodchips + coal	BA	CZT Litoměřice (CZTL)
CZTM_BA	grate co-combustion	woodchips and sawdust + coal	BA	CZT Mimoň (CZTM)
HO_FA HO_BA	FBC co-combustion	80 % coal + 20 % biomass	FA BA	power plant Hodonín (HO)
PO_FA PO_BA	FBC co-combustion	80 % coal + 20 % biomass	FA BA	power plant Poříčí (PO)

All samples were evaluated for environmental safety using leachability verification tests according to the standard EN 12457-4¹². The sample was prepared in a ratio of material to distilled water of 1:10. Contrary to the standard, solidified samples were not used, but powder samples, i.e. 100 g of powdered material was weighed into plastic containers together with 1000 ml of distilled water. The container was sealed and placed in an overhead shaker for 24±0.5 hours, after which each mixture was filtered.

To evaluate the leachability of dangerous chemical substances, the strictest values were selected from TP ASVEP¹³, TP 93¹¹ and Decree 273/2021 Sb.¹⁴ with leachability classes I and IIa. Class I is defined for inert material – landfill S-IO (inert). Class IIa is defined for other waste S-OO1. The binding limits are set by Decree 273/2021 Sb., which specifies the maximum permissible values of dangerous chemical substances released in the case of waste disposal in landfills, and TP 93 in the case of material use for the design and construction of roads using fly ash and bottom ash. The TP ASVEP limits can only be considered as recommended values. Table II shows the limit values for leached substances. The colour-coded values in Tables III and IV do not meet the relevant evaluation criteria, and their colour coding corresponds to the header of Table II.

Table II: Limit values for leachates according to the relevant criteria, leachate values given in mg/l, electrical conductivity in mS.m⁻¹.

parametr	class I	class IIa	TP ASVEP	TP 93	parametr	class I	class IIa	TP ASVEP	TP 93
pH	≥6	-	6-9	-	Co	-	-	0,003	0,1
EC	-	-	125	-	Cd	0,004	0,5	0,0005	0,005
TDS	400	8000	-	-	Cr	0,05	7	0,05	0,1
SIS	-	-	-	-	Cu	0,2	10	0,014	1
DOC	50	80	10	-	Hg	0,001	0,2	0,0002	0,005
Cl ⁻	80	1500	-	-	Mo	0,05	3	0,005	-
F ⁻	1	30	-	-	Ni	0,04	4	0,02	0,1
SO _x	100	3000	-	-	Pb	0,05	5	0,005	0,1
Al	-	-	0,2	-	Sb	0,006	0,5	0,005	-
Ag	-	-	-	0,1	Se	0,01	0,7	0,01	0,05
As	0,05	2,5	0,01	0,1	Sn	-	-	0,025	1
B	-	-	0,3	-	V	-	-	0,018	0,2
Ba	2	30	0,05	1	Zn	0,4	20	0,15	3

Be	-	-	-	0,005
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The pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS) at 105 °C, soluble inorganic salts (SIS) and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) were measured in all samples. Trace elements were also measured using ICP: antimony, arsenic, barium, beryllium, boron, tin, aluminium, cadmium, chromium, cobalt, lead, copper, molybdenum, nickel, mercury, selenium, silver, vanadium and zinc. Finally, chlorides, fluorides and sulphates were monitored using ion liquid chromatography.

Results and discussion

Table III shows the measured values for pH, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, soluble inorganic salts and dissolved organic carbon for all samples. Colour coded values exceed limits according to the header of Table II. The measured values show that most samples exceed the values for total dissolved solids according to Decree 273/2021 Sb. class I (red font), regardless of the type of combustion. In samples from the grate combustion of pure biomass LBP and JH, this parameter is also exceeded according to class IIa of Decree 273/2021 Sb. (red highlighting). Furthermore, most samples from grate combustion exceed the values for pH and electrical conductivity according to TP ASVEP (blue highlighting). Some samples from this type of combustion and locations exceed the dissolved organic carbon parameter.

Based on these data, it is clear that none of the fly and the bottom ash from biomass combustion or co-combustion complies with Decree 237/2021 Sb. and is therefore not suitable for storage in S-other landfills as other waste S-001.

When compared with the results for coal ash¹⁵, the analysed BMA samples, especially those from grate combustion of pure biomass, generally have a higher pH (coal ash pH 7.38 – 8.23), which indicates significant alkalinity, probably caused by a higher CaO content. All samples also show significantly higher electrical conductivity compared to coal ash (241 mS.m⁻¹), which indicates a high degree of leachability of ions contained in the materials, as evidenced by another parameter, TDS, which is exceeded in all samples. When comparing BMA and coal ash (TDS 2220–2430 mg/l), the values for fly ash from grate combustion are visibly higher, up to fivefold higher. In some samples of fly and bottom ash from co-combustion, the values are slightly higher.

Table III: Ash leachability results – pH, EC, TDS, SIS and DOC: leachate values given in mg/l, electrical conductivity in mS.m⁻¹.

sample	pH	EC	TDS	SIS	DOC
LBP_FA_1	12.8	1510	7040	6500	5.02
LBP_FA_2	12.8	1760	8160	7580	6.06
LBP_FA_3	12.7	1360	5440	5090	5.54
LBP_BA_1	9.51	622	8240	6510	12.9
LBP_BA_2	8.0	439	5200	4100	17.8
LBP_BA_3	8.13	213	1960	1680	2.12
JH_FA+BA_1	9.96	879	5890	5660	2.54
JH_FA+BA_2	10.5	1440	11400	10700	15
JH_FA+BA_3	10.5	1440	11400	10700	15
CZTL_BA_1	8.29	67.1	504	455	1.9
CZTM_BA_1	8.49	152	1040	962	2.02
HO_FA_1	12.7	997	4190	3840	4.63
HO_FA_2	12.6	908	3990	3690	3.09
HO_FA_3	12.6	831	2830	2820	2.3
HO_BA_1	11.6	91.7	286	220	2.41
HO_BA_2	12.6	931	4340	4060	2.93
HO_BA_3	12.3	391	910	876	3.28
PO_FA_1	9.34	267	2310	1960	2.52
PO_FA_2	12.4	740	2720	2370	3.97
PO_FA_3	12.5	878	3170	2720	3.63
PO_BA_1	11.7	90.5	346	332	2.2
PO_BA_2	12.7	959	4250	3970	2.83
PO_BA_3	11.8	147	406	362	2.51

Table IV shows the results of trace element leachability, where the limit values were exceeded and this exceedance is color coded according to the table header II.

The results show that for most samples, regardless of the type of combustion, the limit for sulphates according to class I (red font) was exceeded. In samples from LBP grate combustion, this limit was also exceeded according to class IIa (red highlighting). In FBC biomass co-combustion, it can be seen that the limit is exceeded more significantly for fly ash than bottom ash.

Most fly ash samples exceeded the limits for chlorides according to class I (red font). Fly ash samples from Jindřichův Hradec (JH) also exceeded this limit according to class IIa (red highlighting). Several fly and bottom ash samples exceeded the limit for fluorides.

Furthermore, most samples did not comply with the molybdenum content, which was not exceeded in only two bottom ash samples. Other elements for which the samples did not meet the requirements were aluminium, boron, barium, mercury, lead, antimony, selenium and vanadium.

Samples from FBC co-combustion of biomass from Hodonín (HO) and Poříčí (PO) exceeded the chromium content limit. Samples from the grate combustion of pure biomass from Energetické centrum s.r.o. Jindřichův Hradec exceeded the arsenic content limit.

When comparing BMA samples with coal ash¹⁵, the limits for the same trace elements (As, B, Ba, Mo, Se, V and Al for fly ash) were exceeded. BMA samples from grate combustion show a higher sulphate content.

In general, according to Decree 273/2021 Sb., it can be stated that:

most input materials, regardless of the type of combustion and resulting ash, do not meet the definition of inert material (class I) in terms of total dissolved solids content. Samples from grate combustion of pure biomass from Lenzing Biocel Paskov a.s. and Energetické centrum s.r.o. Jindřichův Hradec do not meet the definition of other waste (class IIa) in terms of total dissolved solids content. Furthermore, most samples, regardless of the type of combustion, do not meet the definition of inert material (class I) in terms of chloride, fluoride, sulphate, molybdenum and selenium content. Fly ash has worse results than bottom ash. Samples from FBC co-combustion from Hodonín and Poříčí do not comply in terms of chromium content. Samples from the grate combustion of pure biomass from Energetické centrum s.r.o. Jindřichův Hradec have a higher arsenic content. Some samples from the grate combustion of pure biomass from the Lenzing Biocel Paskov a.s. and Energetické centrum s.r.o. Jindřichův Hradec sites do not comply with the definition of other waste (class IIa) in terms of chloride and sulphate content.

According to Decree 273/2021 Sb., only bottom ash samples from FBC co-combustion of biomass with coal from the Hodonín and Poříčí would qualify as waste S-OO1 for landfilling. No sample would meet the requirements of a further evaluation according to the technical conditions of TP ASVEP, which are stricter than Decree 273/2021 Sb.

In terms of use in the construction industry, according to TP 93, the samples meet the parameters and are suitable materials. The exceptions are samples CZTL and CZTM from co-combustion, which exceed the limit for selenium and vanadium. One bottom ash sample from Hodonín and fly ash samples from Poříčí, i.e. samples from FBC co-combustion, exceed the limit for chromium.

It should be noted that the leachate samples were not prepared exactly by Decree 273/2021 Sb., where the leachate is made from a solidified sample, but a procedure was chosen to obtain the leachate directly from a powder sample. This procedure is the least favourable in terms of leachability results, but it shows the worst possible leachability values for the materials.

Table IV: Ash leachability results – trace elements: leachate values given in mg/l

sample	Cl	F	SO _x	Al	As	B	Ba	Cr	Hg	Mo	Pb	Sb	Se	V
LBP_FA_1	117	0.72	2080	<0.010	<0.001	0.184	0.23	0.011	0.00006	0.117	<0.001	<0.0010	0.007	<0.001
LBP_FA_2	145	<1.000	2780	<0.020	<0.002	0.317	0.217	0.015	0.00025	0.15	0.005	<0.0010	0.010	<0.001
LBP_FA_3	50	0.852	1710	<0.010	<0.001	0.238	0.218	0.012	0.00027	0.246	0.001	<0.0010	0.005	<0.001
LBP_BA_1	3.4	<0.200	5160	<0.010	<0.001	0.113	0.039	0.004	<0.0000	0.003	<0.001	0.0028	<0.005	<0.001
LBP_BA_2	1.31	<0.200	3320	<0.010	0.002	0.214	0.041	0.008	<0.0000	0.02	<0.001	0.0022	0.011	0.002
LBP_BA_3	1.06	0.232	1320	<0.010	0.002	0.155	0.043	0.003	<0.0000	0.008	<0.001	0.0015	0.006	0.002
JH_FA+BA_1	1310	<0.400	1140	<0.010	0.057	0.265	0.018	0.017	<0.0000	0.145	<0.001	0.0015	0.006	0.013
JH_FA+BA_2	1790	<0.500	2440	<0.010	0.051	0.55	0.007	0.004	0.00002	0.23	<0.001	0.0015	0.009	0.022
JH_FA+BA_3	1790	<0.500	2440	<0.010	0.051	0.55	0.007	0.004	0.00002	0.23	<0.001	0.0015	0.009	0.022
CZTL_BA_1	<1.00	1.36	314	0.016	0.031	4.22	0.076	0.001	<0.0000	0.024	<0.001	0.0011	0.080	0.21
CZTM_BA_1	<1.00	3.62	703	0.428	0.047	2.51	0.06	0.003	<0.0000	0.171	<0.001	0.0017	0.290	0.248
HO_FA_1	139	0.888	1280	<0.010	<0.001	0.068	0.189	0.057	0.00003	0.079	<0.001	<0.0010	0.010	<0.001
HO_FA_2	73.4	0.816	1580	<0.010	<0.001	<0.050	0.262	0.124	0.00001	0.086	<0.001	<0.0010	0.011	0.002
HO_FA_3	166	1.36	533	0.018	<0.001	<0.050	0.308	0.098	0.00002	0.084	0.008	<0.0010	0.005	<0.001
HO_BA_1	<1.00	<0.200	20.1	2.07	<0.001	0.185	0.188	0.003	0.00001	0.005	<0.001	0.0027	<0.005	0.011
HO_BA_2	<1.20	<0.400	1630	<0.010	<0.001	0.092	0.181	0.004	0.00006	0.048	<0.001	<0.0010	<0.005	<0.001
HO_BA_3	1.83	<0.200	<5.00	0.461	<0.001	<0.020	0.16	0.007	<0.0000	0.007	<0.001	0.0025	<0.005	0.005
PO_FA_1	181	0.601	1160	0.12	0.001	1.76	0.387	0.152	0.00002	0.041	<0.001	0.0052	0.012	0.016
PO_FA_2	5.8	3.27	864	0.011	<0.001	<0.050	0.533	0.17	0.00027	0.123	<0.001	<0.0010	0.021	0.008
PO_FA_3	128	0.836	901	<0.010	<0.001	<0.050	0.225	0.185	0.00001	0.104	0.003	<0.0010	0.007	<0.001
PO_BA_1	1.08	<0.200	11.4	0.669	<0.001	0.242	0.102	0.003	0.00001	0.006	<0.001	0.0043	<0.005	0.013
PO_BA_2	<1.20	<0.400	1700	<0.010	<0.001	<0.050	0.179	0.016	0.00002	0.045	<0.001	<0.0010	<0.005	<0.001
PO_BA_3	<1.00	<0.200	8.57	0.862	<0.001	0.198	0.123	0.004	<0.0000	0.008	<0.001	0.0039	<0.005	0.009

Conclusion

Based on the analyses performed, it can be stated that ash samples from biomass co-combustion show better results in terms of leachability compared to ash from biomass grate combustion. However, none of these ashes meet the conditions set by the waste decree for landfilling under Czech legislation. Nevertheless, it can be assumed that ash in a solidified form could comply with the legislation. The results obtained also indicate the potential for using ash from combustion and co-combustion of biomass in the construction industry, as stated in TP 93: Design and Construction of Road Structures Using Fly Ash and Bottom Ash, and could represent an environmentally and economically advantageous solution for their further material use.

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